

PHYTOCHEMICAL STANDERIZATION AND ANTIDIARRHOEAL ACTIVITY OF GUM FROM *PTEROCARPUS MARSUPIUM*

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ABSTRACT

The gum of the *Pterocarpus marsupium* plant has been shown to have antidiarrheal action, which is one of its significant medicinal potentials. A common condition of the gastrointestinal tract, diarrhea is characterized by frequent feces that are loose or watery and is often accompanied by stomach pain and discomfort. If it is not addressed, it may cause you to get dehydrated and throw off your electrolyte balance. Natural products, such as the gum obtained from the *Pterocarpus marsupium* tree, have been investigated for their possible antidiarrheal benefits. These natural products provide a safer and more cost-effective alternative to traditional pharmaceuticals. The effectiveness of *Pterocarpus marsupium* gum as an antidiarrheal treatment has been the subject of several investigations, both preclinical and clinical. According to the findings of this research, it can decrease the frequency of bowel movements, enhance stool consistency, and relieve related discomfort. Modulation of intestinal motility, regulation of fluid secretion, and decreased intestinal inflammation are the underlying mechanisms of action at work here.

The fact that *Pterocarpus marsupium* gum contains a variety of bioactive elements is one of the reasons why it may have positive effects on one's health. The presence of antioxidant and anti-inflammatory qualities in flavonoids, such as quercetin and kaempferol, may be beneficial in lowering the levels of oxidative stress and inflammation linked with diarrhea. Tannins, on the other hand, have astringent characteristics that may aid in tightening and calming the intestinal lining, hence minimizing excessive fluid loss and facilitating regular bowel movements. Tannins are found in fruits and vegetables.

Keywords: Phytochemical, Pharmacological Activities, Anti-Diabetic, Anti-Diarrhoeal.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, a great amount of attention has been paid to the phytochemical standardization and assessment of the biological activities of natural products owing to the potential medicinal uses of these natural products. In this context, the gum that is produced from the medicinal plant *Pterocarpus marsupium*, which has a long history of traditional usage, has arisen as a topic of attention^[1]. The gum of the *Pterocarpus marsupium* plant has been shown to have antidiarrheal action, which is one of its significant medicinal potentials. A common condition of the gastrointestinal tract, diarrhea is characterized by frequent feces that are loose or watery and is often accompanied by stomach pain and discomfort.^[2]

The use of natural gums in antidiarrheal formulations offers several potential benefits, including biocompatibility, low toxicity, and the potential for extended drug release. *Pterocarpus marsupium* gum can be formulated into various dosage forms, such as tablets, capsules, or suspensions. This versatility makes it easier for patients to take their medication, thereby increasing the likelihood that they will adhere to dosing instructions.^[3]

Diarrhea

Diarrhea is defined by an increase in stool volume or fluidity, a change in stool consistency, and a rise in the frequency of bowel movements. Diagnosis is most effectively based on observing **stool frequency, rather than attempting to measure stool fluid content, which can be unrealistic.** The World Health Organization considers three or more episodes of diarrhea within a 24-hour period to be clinically significant.^[4] In addition to the loss of electrolytes and water, diarrhea leads to increased motility and secretion in the gastrointestinal system, while reducing the absorption of fluids. It's important to note that constipation can occur when feces move too rapidly through the colon, which can actually cause diarrhea.^[5]

Types of diarrhoea

Microbiological toxins, vasoactive intestinal polypeptides, excessive bile acids, laxatives, and unabsorbed fat have all been linked to Secretory diarrhea.

Methodology

Plant material

Indian Kino Tree, Malabar Tree, Vijayasar, Bija, and Asana are all names for the same tree, *Petrocarpus Marsupium* Roxb.-Fabaceae (PM).

PM Gum-Kino has been used to treat diarrhoea, dysentery, leucorrhoea, etc.; and PM bark has been used as an astringent and to treat toothaches.

Extraction

The powder was extracted using ethanol as a solvent in a soxhlet apparatus. The extract obtained was dried on a water bath followed by drying in oven at 40° C until completely dried. The yield of the ethanolic Gum extract was found to be 18.01% .

6.5 Phytochemical studies

Preliminary phytochemical screening

Preliminary qualitative phytochemical screening using standard test was done in methanol reconstituted extract to find out the presence of phytoconstituents.

Toxic effects

Because of its astringent nature, PM is not recommended for usage in cases of constipation. Since the diabetic herbal therapy is administered over a longer period of time, PM's genotoxicity was evaluated in both somatic and germ cells. A lack of genotoxicity was found in the extract.

Pharmacological Evaluation

Analgesic control

Anti-bacterial control

Anti-cancer control

Anti-cataract control

Anti-diabetic control

Anti-fungal control

Anti-hyperlipidemic control

Anti-inflammatory control

Anti-oxidant control

Cardiotonic control

RESULT

Extraction of Plant Material

The powder was extracted using ethanol as a solvent in a soxhlet apparatus. The extract obtained was dried on a water bath followed by drying in oven at 40° C until completely dried. The yield of the ethanolic Gum extract was found to be 18.01% .

Phytochemical Screening of the Extract

The preliminary qualitative phytochemical screening of the dried alcoholic extract was done on the dried extract reconstituted by ethanol and checked the presence of phytoconstituents.

Value of Physicochemical Parameters Results

The quality of the Gum used for the study was checked by performing physical according to the monograph of British pharmacopeia. The test results indicated that the dried Gum used for the study complied with the limits for the physical tests as per the monograph in British Pharmacopeia. The results are shown in table 4.1. On the other side extractive value of the Gum powder was carried out by different solvents and the maximum extractive 18.01±0.09 % w/w was observed with ethanol.

Effect of EEPM on castor-oil induced diarrhoea in rat

Diarrhoea induced with castor oil showed significant increase in the total number of feces. EEPM at a dose of 250 and 500 mg/kg were significantly reduced the total number of feces (6.2 ± 0.96 ; $p < 0.01$ and 3.4 ± 0.82 ; $p < 0.001$; respectively). This is comparable with the reference drug loperamide (2.4 ± 0.57 ; $p < 0.001$).

Effect of EEPM on gastrointestinal motility in rat

Treatment with EEPM at a dose of 250 and 500 mg/kg were significantly (75.80 ± 1.06 $p < 0.01$ and 68.80 ± 8.89 ; $p < 0.001$; respectively) reduced the gastrointestinal motility in rats. This is comparable with the reference drug atropine (67.60 ± 2.11 ; $p < 0.001$).

Effect on Castor Oil-induced Diarrhoea at different dose levels:

In the castor oil-induced diarrhoeal model in rat, the 95% ethanolic extract at the 200 & 400 mg/kg dose levels were found to reduce the severity of diarrhoea in test animals. There was less significant effect with the dose of 200 mg/kg (p.o.) of the extract compared with control. The reduction on castor oil-induced diarrhoea at 400 mg/kg (p.o.) of plant extract treatment was found to be almost comparable with that of treatment by 3 mg/kg of loperamide.

Discussion

Phytochemical Studies

The goal of the current research is to determine whether or not an ethanolic extract of *Pterocarpus marsupium* heartwood may alleviate the diarrhoea caused by castor oil in laboratory animals. It has been determined via phytochemical analysis that EEPM contains glycosides, carbohydrates, flavonoids, and tannins.

Medicinal properties

Medicinal herbs with antidiarrheal properties contain tannins, flavonoids, alkaloids, saponins, lowering sugar, sterols, and terpenes. Flavonoids reduce abnormal intestinal movements and secretions, inhibit prostaglandin E₂-induced secretions, and have antioxidant properties that inhibit various enzymes. *Pterocarpus marsupium*'s ethanolic extract may have antidiarrheal properties due to these components.

Pharmacological Effect

This study's findings support the use of *Pterocarpus marsupium* heartwood extract for the treatment of diarrhoea due to the presence of pharmacologically active compounds. Potential ingredients for cutting-edge pharmaceuticals might be found in these attributes. More research is needed to isolate, identify, and characterise the many active chemicals present in the extract and to determine how they function.

Conclusion

This investigation tested the effectiveness of a recently discovered herb against Wistar albino rat diarrhea caused by an injection of castor oil. It is well known that castor oil, or more specifically, ricinoleic acid, causes a hypersecretory reaction and diarrhoea by altering the permeability of

mucosal fluid and electrolyte transport. The PGE-2 concentration in the gut lumen was significantly raised by ricinoleic acid, and net secretion of water and electrolytes into the small intestine was similarly enhanced. Castor oil's ricinoleic acid causes intestinal mucosal irritation and inflammation, which triggers the production of prostaglandins that increase intestinal motility and secretion.

An initial investigation of diarrhea in test animals showed that the 95% ethanolic extract of certain plant components has anti-diarrheal properties. The gathered data offers experimental support for the effectiveness of various traditional medicines as anti-diarrheal agents. However, further research involving bioassay-guided phytochemical and pharmacological studies is needed to identify the active principles and specific mechanisms of action.

Figures and Tables

Table 1.

Table 2.

Table 3.

Figure 1.

Figure 2.

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Table 1. Qualitative analysis of Gum of *Pterocarpus marsupium* extracts

S No.	Plant Constituents	Qualitative tests	Pet Ether extract	Chloroform extract	Ethyl acetate extract	Methanolic extract	Alcoholic extract	Aqueous extract
1.	Alkaloids	Mayer's test	-	-	-	+	-	-
		Dragendroff's Test	-	-	-	+	+	-
		Wagner's test	-	-	-	+	-	-
		Hager's test	-	-	-	+	-	-
2.	Carbohydrates	Molish test	-	-	-	+	+	-
		Fehlings test	-	-	-	+	+	-
		Barfoed test	-	-	-	+	+	-
		Benedict test	-	-	-	+	+	-
3.	Glycosides	General test	-	+	+	+	+	-
		Borntrager's test	-	+	+	+	+	-
		Keller-Killiani test	+	-	+	+	+	-
4.	Saponins	Foam test	-	-	-	+	+	-
		Ferric chloride test	+	-	+	+	+	-

5.	Phenolic compounds	Zinc-Hydrochloride reduction test	+	-	+	+	+	-
		Lead acetate test	-	-	-	+	+	-
6.	Flavonoids	Ferric chloride test	+	+	+	+	+	+
		Shinoda test	-	-	+	+	+	-
		Zinc-Hydrochloride reduction test	+	-	+	+	+	+
		Alkaline reagent-test	-	-	+	+	+	-
7.	Tannins	Ferric chloride test	+	-	-	+	+	+
		Vanillin Hydrochloride test	-	-	-	+	+	-
		Alkaline reagent-test	-	-	-	+	+	-
8.	Triterpenes	Salkowski test	+	-	-	+	+	-
9.	Steroids	Salkowski's test	+	-	-	-	+	-
		Lieberman Burchardt tests	-	+	-	+	+	-
10.	Proteins & Amino acids	Millon's Test	-	-	-	-	-	-
		Ninhydrin test	-	-	-	-	-	-

Table 2. Effect of Pterocarpus marsupium extract on castor-oil induced diarrhoea in rat.

Group	Total number of feces	Inhibition of diarrhoea (%)
Group-I	13.58 ± 1.88	--
Group-II	6.1 ± 0.96 *	54.38
Group-III	3.7 ± 0.792 **	76
Group-IV	2.6 ± 0.59 **	79

Table 3. Effect of EPM on gastrointestinal motility in rat.

Group	Distance travelled by Charcoal meal (cm)	Inhibition of diarrhoea (%)
Group-I	86.20± 2.28	--
Group-II	75.80± 3.06	↓ 12.00
Group-III	68.80± 1.89 **	↓20.18
Group-IV	67.60± 2.11 **	↓22.27

Values are expressed as mean ± S.E.M (n = 5), where **p < 0.01, when compared to the control.

Figure 1: Effect of EPM on castor-oil induced diarrhoea in rat

Figure 2: Effect of EPM on gastrointestinal motility in rat